

Users Guide for the Jupiter Energetic Particle Detector Instrument (JEDI) on NASA's Juno Mission (Version 3)

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Introduction

Here we address the response of the Jupiter Energetic particle Detector Instrument (JEDI) on NASA's Juno mission to electron and ion distributions that are extreme in various ways (energy, intensity, angular structure, penetrating radiation, etc.). JEDI is documented in Mauk et al. (2017a), generated prior to Juno's encounter with Jupiter. We have learned much during the ongoing mission.

We consider first anomalies that occur within the JEDI electron measurements. Electrons are measured by JEDI using solid-state detectors (SSDs) that are 0.50 mm thick and that are attached on the back to a thick shield of Tungsten-Copper (that can redirect some escaping electrons back into the SSDs). The fact that some electrons can fully penetrate and leave the detector causes a distortion in the measured spectra. We have developed a procedure described here to correct the contaminated spectra. This same procedure

provides a method of clearly discriminating between sharp features caused by auroral acceleration and sharp features that can be caused by the penetrators. This same procedure also provides a technique for identifying some regions of saturation, where the sensor cannot process electron events fast enough to reconstruct the original spectral shapes at the lower energies. We also address the issues of very high energy electrons that penetrate the sides of the sensor volume, and the measurement of very narrow electron angular features. For electrons, we finally address the issue of the occasional proton contamination of the electron distributions. The 2 micron of aluminum flashing on the surface of the electron solid-state-detectors provides an imperfect protection from such contamination.

We also address here issues related to the measurement of ion distributions. Ion measurements are more robust than electron measurements because of the use of coincident circuitry. Here, multiple, near simultaneous, signals must be received before an event is considered valid. However, the circuitry can be overwhelmed with what are termed "accidentals", whereby the multiple elements of the coincident circuitry can be overwhelmed with random events.

We finally provide a substantial list of additional features of which users should be aware before using JEDI data.

This document is Version 3 of the JEDI Users Guide. Previous versions of this JEDI Users Guide were published as Supporting Information in Mauk et al. (2018; Version 1) and then Mauk et al. (2023; Version 2).

Text S1. SSD electron penetration contamination of electrons

Here we present a procedure that has been used in the literature to correct the JEDI-measured electron spectra that are contaminated with high energy foreground electrons that penetrate the detectors. New procedures are being developed, as discussed at the very end of this section. By foreground we mean electrons that enter by means of the appropriate collimator openings. This issue is different than the one regarding the electron penetration of the side walls of the JEDI instrument (See Text 5), although such side-wall penetrating particle will contribute to the process described here. Note that this procedure is only verified and likely useful for the JEDI large electron pixels. There are non-linearities to the responses of the small electron pixels that limit their use for accurate quantitative analysis. See Text S10, Item 24.

The minimum energy of an electron that can fully penetrate the JEDI SSDs is about 400 keV. If an electron penetrates the detector, it does not deposit all of its energy in the detector and therefore the deposited energy does not correctly characterize the measured electron. While electrons above 400 keV can penetrate the detector, many do not because electrons scatter within the detector, so that electron energies much higher than 400 keV can be measured on a statistical probability basis. Effectively, the

measurement of electrons above 400 keV can be book-kept by using an efficiency. The drop in efficiency for electrons with energies that exceed the penetration depth of the solid-state detector has been determined empirically and is parameterized here as an efficiency.

$$Effpen = 1 - Exp \left[-2 \left(\frac{480}{E_{keV}} \right)^3 \right] \quad (1)$$

where E_{keV} is the kinetic energy of the incoming electron. The technique for empirically establishing this expression and the expressions that follow was to run the entire procedure described here on many different spectra while varying the parameters of the expressions. Success was declared when good fitting results were achieved with a single set of parameters for wide diversity of spectral shapes and intensity values. Note that this high energy tail correction to the JEDI data (Equation 1) was not applied to the archived JEDI data for data collected early in the mission. Later in the mission it has been applied and will be applied to earlier data when and if that data is reprocessed. Data generated since we started doing this correction as part of the processing have a keyword EFFCOR. If it is set to T, the correction has already been applied. If it is set to F, or if that keyword is missing altogether, the correction was not applied. This is a reliable way to know for sure whether the high energy tail was corrected on a file-by-file basis. And so, to apply the full procedure describe here for data processed with the Equation (1) correction, one must first remove the correction given with Equation (1), or otherwise be aware that that correction has been made.

Every electron that fully penetrates the detector leaves behind a contribution to the minimum ionizing bump in the spectrum (Figure S1A). In other words, the count rate in the vicinity of 150 keV is the sum of the count rate of electrons at that energy and the count rate of penetrating electrons that deposit that much energy before they exit the SSD. The shape of the minimum ionizing feature is insensitive to the shape of the penetrating electron spectrum because the energy deposition per unit distance (the so-called dE/dX function, called the stopping power) is very flat at these energies, and specifically between 0.25 and 10 MeV (e. g. NIST, 2017; Zombeck, 2007). But, it is not exactly flat, and there are other details (degree of scattering for penetrating electrons with different energies) that lead to some small dependencies of the minimum ionizing peak to the penetrating spectrum. At this point in the development, we assume that the shape of the minimum ionizing spectrum is universal and unchanging. It has been determined empirically and is parameterized here with the following analytic equation:

$$MIfunc = \frac{Func1 \times Func2}{35.47} \quad (2)$$

where

$$Func1 = \frac{(1 + Tanh[0.1 (E_{keV} - 112)])^2}{4}$$

$$Func2 = Exp \left[\frac{-(EkeV - 85)}{60} \right]$$

Here the "35.47" is the normalization factor that makes the area under Mlfunc equal to 1 (the reason for this factor will become apparent below). This function does not perfectly reproduce the bump in the observed spectra. For the reasons described above, we find that sometimes the peak of the observed minimum ionizing function is slightly higher or lower than the peak parameterized here.

Our procedure is to use a parameterized functional form for the input energetic electron spectrum. The form that we use, found previously to fit a wide variety of magnetospheric particle spectra (see Mauk and Fox, (2010, for electrons and Mauk (2014 for ions), is a kappa distribution (in the non-relativistic regime) normalized with an additional power-law break at higher energies. Note that we use this function only for energies greater than about 78 or 90 keV (spectrum dependent); we leave the points below that energy unchanged since those energies have nothing to do with the effects that we are trying to model. The spectrum has the form:

$$Intensity = \frac{C EkeV [kT (g1 + 1) + EkeV]^{-(g1-1)}}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{EkeV}{Eo} \right)^{g2} \right]} \quad (3)$$

where EkeV is energy in keV. Here the free parameters that we must optimize are C, kT, g1, Eo, and g2. The units on the intensity are 1/(cm² s sr keV).

In the procedure developed here, we keep a careful accounting of particles that are lost and gained. Every particle that is lost (not counted at its actual energy) because it penetrates the detector shows up as a single particle contribution to the minimum ionizing peak. We therefore must know how many particles are lost, not just within the nominal energy range of JEDI, but to much higher energies as well. We therefore must determine the following integral, where PLost is the number of electrons per time that are not detected close to their actual energy, over the area and solid angle of the instrument.

$$PLost = \int_{Elow}^{Ehigh} Intensity \times (1 - Effpen) dEkeV \quad (4)$$

from Elow (any energy that is lower than those that can penetrate the detector; e. g. use 30 keV) to Infinity (or a very large number, Ehigh). *Intensity* (Equation 3) refers to the ambient (not measured) distribution of electrons and describes their number at their actual energy, per time, energy range, detector area and solid angle. Note that if the power law of the high energy tail of the incoming electron distribution at the highest

energies ($g1 + g2$ for Equation 3) becomes small enough (close to the value of 1) then the parameter PLost becomes unconstrained (diverges as one integrates to infinity) and the procedure fails.

The procedure now is to optimize the parameters in Intensity (Equation 3) such that we fit the observed spectrum with the following function:

$$\text{Fit} = \text{Intensity} \times \text{Effpen} + \text{PLost} \times \text{Mlfunc} \quad (5)$$

The factor Effpen removes electrons from their ambient energy within the high energy tail, and the second term adds these electrons into the minimum ionizing feature.

Just as an example, this procedure is easy to implement for single spectra in the software Excel using the Solver subprogram (sample available on request). An example of such an optimization for a highly contaminated spectrum is shown in Figure S1A. Here the individual blue symbols are the original data, the solid blue line is the fit (Equation 5) to the data for energies greater than 78 keV. The red line is the input spectra (Equation 3) that has had its parameters optimized to yield the best fit of the blue solid line to the data (blue symbols). The final result (shown in Figure S1B) comprises the original data for energies up to about 90 keV, and the reconstructed data using the red line for energy greater than or equal to 78 keV. We have not succeeded in generating a robust automated procedure because, given limited resources, our procedures to date have difficulty in distinguishing between electrostatic auroral acceleration and the minimum ionizing peak. As described in Text S3, the hands-on procedure, with the human mind making the judgements, does not have the same problem.

There are tricks to obtaining the most robust fits over all energies. Our error function that must be minimized uses the logarithm of the intensity values ($\text{Error} = \text{Sum}[\text{Log}(\text{model}) - \text{Log}(\text{data})]^2$). A robust procedure sometimes requires that the sensitivity of the error function to the various parameters be flattened out. One way of doing that is to rewrite Equation (3) into something like:

$$\text{Intensity} = \frac{10^{LC} \frac{EkeV}{100} \left(\frac{kT}{100} (g1 + 1) + \frac{EkeV}{100} \right)^{(-g1-1)}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{EkeV}{Eo} \right)^{g2} \right)} \quad (6)$$

Here, the energies have been normalized by an energy parameter (100 in this case) that is contained within the range of energies under consideration, a normalization that reduces the sensitivity of the error function to the $g1$ parameter. In this version we are also optimizing the log of the normalizing parameter (LC) rather than the normalizing parameter itself (C), thereby increasing the sensitivity of the error function to the normalizing parameter.

New, more complicated procedures are being developed on the basis of GEANT4 simulations of JEDI's response to penetrators, as documented in Zhu et al. (2025). For omnidirectional spectra, one may use the derived energy-dependent geometric factors to optimize parametric spectral shapes with the energy-dependent channel count rates. To date, this process would include contributions from electrons that penetrate the side walls of JEDI, contributions discussed in Text S5.

Text S2. SSD penetration effects on electron moments

Here we discuss the effect of electrons that fully penetrate the JEDI solid state detectors on the calculation of moments of the electron distributions.

An important parameter for addressing the impact of energetic electrons on auroral physics is the energy flux that precipitates down onto the atmosphere. The procedure for calculating this parameter has been described elsewhere (Mauk et al., 2017b). But an important consideration is how that parameter might be modified by the distortions that arise from the penetrating particles. It turns out that if we do no correction, and just use only the original uncorrected data (including not applying equation 1, which is sometimes already applied to the archived data; see Text S1), we obtain a lower limit to the energy flux for electron energies >30 keV. That outcome occurs because the electrons that are lost within the >400 keV higher energy tail (including those above the nominal energy range of JEDI) are all counted, but their energies are reassigned to a lower value, close to 150 keV. Figure S2 shows, in black, the "lower limit" to the energy flux described here (this figure is the top panel of Figure 3 in Mauk et al.; 2018). Note that the number flux that one would obtain by simply integrating the original uncorrected data will be close to the correct value for >30 keV electrons, since the energy assigned to the particles is not relevant to that parameter. Only the very small percentage of > 1.2 MeV electrons that are fully stopped by the detector are not counted because there is no channel accumulation for such electrons. Hence a characteristic energy (E_c), defined as the ratio of energy flux to number flux, is also a lower limit, when using uncorrected data.

In order to further constrain the energy flux in an automated way we have, in Figure S2 and shown in red, partially corrected the data by applying the efficiency factor in Equation (1) but not trying to subtract off the minimum ionizing peak. The integral of that partially corrected spectrum yields an upper limit to the energy flux with respect to integration over the energies measured by JEDI. Hence, Figure S2 shows both a lower limit and an upper limit, to the extent that the spectra are not saturated (see Section S4). We see that these two limits are fairly close to each other, indicating that the energy flux moment is fairly well constrained for situations where the minimum ionizing feature is observed.

Text S3. Distinguishing electron auroral acceleration from electron SSD penetration

Here we discuss the procedure for cleanly distinguishing between the sharp spectral feature that is caused by high energy electrons that penetrate the JEDI solid state detectors and the sharp spectral features caused by electrostatic auroral acceleration.

Figure S1A shows that penetrating electrons give rise to a peaked feature that might potentially be mistaken for coherent auroral acceleration. But what we have found is that when a true coherent downward auroral acceleration occurs, it is seldom accompanied by a high energy tail sufficient to give a substantial minimum ionizing peak. The procedure documented in Section S1 can be used to test this premise. Figure S1C shows an example where a strong auroral acceleration feature is present (this is spectrum 5 in Figure 5 of Mauk et al., 2018). Here we have run our procedure but have artificially eliminated the data points between about 130 and 350 keV (corresponding to the auroral acceleration feature) to see how much of a minimum ionizing peak the high energy tail can produce. The minimum ionizing contamination is the very small bump that represents the difference between the solid blue line and the solid red line. This bump is clearly different from the main peak shown in the unconnected symbols, and therefore, for this case, inconsequential for characterizing the auroral acceleration feature.

With more recent studies (Mauk et al., 2024) we have found that the fortuitous situation generally found with downward electrostatic electron auroral acceleration (whereby electrostatically accelerated peaked electron distributions tend not to be contaminated and confused with a minimum ionizing feature, as described above), does not hold for upward acceleration. At times there are upward electrostatically accelerated electron features that are indeed confused and contaminated with the minimum ionizing feature. In these regions it is often the case that coherent electrostatic acceleration is identified above the spacecraft using proton measurements. It is the upward electrostatic acceleration of electrons below the spacecraft that is obscured.

Text S4. Electron measurement saturation

Here we discuss a procedure for determining when the JEDI electron sensors become partially saturated by particle intensities that are higher than the instrument can fully process.

Electron events within JEDI are processed by software in an onboard computer that can process up to about 30,000 events per second. Fast field-programmable gate array (FPGA) based counters, and so-called dead time counters, are used to renormalize the channel rates on the ground, allowing for the proper reconstruction of the electron spectra for rates up to about 10^6 counts per second. These so-called Rate-versus Rate (R v R) corrections, a part of the Level 3 data generation process, include corrections to non-linearities in the responses of sensors and their electronics. The general correction procedures used are documented in Gkioulidou et al. (2023) as applied to a nearly

identical sister instrument, the RBSPICE instrument on NASA's Radiation Belt Storm Probes mission. For even faster rates, proper reconstruction of the spectral intensities and shapes becomes more difficult. Figure S3, showing large and small pixel rates, shows clear evidence of saturation when the fully corrected large-pixel rates get somewhat above 10^6 counts per second.

The same procedure, documented in section S1, can be used to identify additional aspects of the regions where the intensities are too high to be fully quantified by the JEDI sensor, essentially checking for self-consistency of the measurements. An example is shown in Figure S1D (this is spectrum 2 in Figure 5 of Mauk et al., 2018). Here we have blindly applied our spectra correction procedure, and the procedure clearly fails since the blue curve does not match the blue symbols. The high energy tail of the distribution is demanding that there exists a minimum ionizing bump near 150 keV, but the bump is simply not there. In this case the counts per second summed from all of the channels, nominally corrected for a dead time, sum to a little below 10^6 counts per second, near the upper end of the nominal count rate range of the sensors. Electronic pulses within the instrument, stimulated by the individual electron events, are landing on top of each other, and the instrument is not able to correctly detect every particle and identify the appropriate energy bin for each measured event. And more specifically, the energies of the identified events that are binned are smeared-out to some extent, particularly at the lower energies. This process has likely broadened the expected minimum ionizing peak (blue curve in Fig S1D) to the observed distribution (blue symbols). This broadening effect seems to come into play at rates a little below where the saturation identified in Figure S3 is shown.

Note that JEDI was designed to mitigate the problem of saturation should it be determined that a substantial fraction of the main auroral crossings would result in saturation. JEDI SSDs for each of the three instruments have both large and small pixels (with only large or small pixels active at any one time for each species, electrons and ions; Mauk et al., 2017a). The saturation documented here occurred with large pixels. Going to small pixels reduces the count rates by about a factor of about 14-15. Figure S3 shows the relative response of small and large pixels during a saturation event. Text S10, Item 24 discusses non-linear responses of the small electron pixels that limit their use for quantitative analysis.

During Juno's first auroral pass (PJ1) large pixels were used in JEDI-90 and small pixels were used in JEDI-270. Saturation was not detected during PJ1 and thus the decision was made to utilize large pixels on many follow-on subsequent orbits. Small pixels have been used for some later orbits. There are downsides to the use of the small pixels; their responses become somewhat anomalous (again see text section S10, Item 24).

Text S5. Electron side-wall penetration effects on electrons

Here we discuss how to distinguish contamination within the JEDI electron sensors that occurs as a result of electrons that have energies high enough to penetrate the detector shielding, and not just the SSDs as discussed in Text S1.

Solid-State-Detector (SSD) shielding. JEDI external shielding is highly directional. If one excludes the collimator region, the JEDI detectors are shielded mostly by about 7.7 g/cm^2 (200 mil) of an 80/20 mixture (by weight) of Tungsten and Copper (WCu), with a density of about 15.15 g/cm^3 . Detailed analyses using the analytic functional forms in Tabata et al. (2002, for $E[\text{extr}]/r_0$), and the Continuous Slow Down Approximation (CSDA) range, r_0 , from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST, 2017), we estimate that the level of most side (non-collimator) shielding corresponds to an Extrapolated Range energy ($E[\text{extr}]$) of about 21.5 MeV electrons. The "Extrapolated Range" is a convenient way to cross-compare shielding levels with other configurations, but it does not tell the whole story. Very roughly for the materials that we are using (reading numbers off transmissions curves shown in Tabata et al, 2002), a shielding that corresponds to an extrapolated range of $E[\text{extr}]$ excludes about 89% ($\pm 2\%$) of normally impacting electrons with that energy, allowing about 11% of those electrons into the sensitive volume. The energy of electrons that are excluded by 99% is very roughly $0.7 \times E[\text{extr}]$, which for the JEDI situation corresponds to about 15 MeV. All of these estimations are for electrons that strike the JEDI surfaces perpendicular to the surfaces. Higher energies would be needed for non-normal impactors.

Again, not counting the collimator region, there is a small fraction of penetrating trajectories, on the opposite side of the cylindrical structure of the JEDI sensor from the SSDs (see Figure 48 in Mauk et al., 2017a) that can reach the SSDs that are shielded by only 3.9 g/cm^2 of WCu, corresponding to an extrapolated range energy of 10.6 MeV.

The JEDI collimator region has very different levels of shielding and its structure makes it challenging to estimate the penetrating electrons that can get into the JEDI sensor volume and those that are excluded. The collimator comprises 5 cylindrical WCu blades with multiple aligned holes to collimate the incoming particles. Going from the outermost to the innermost blade, they have thickness of about 0.1, 0.05, 0.05, 0.05, and 0.05 cm. If an electron passes through the materials of all 5 blades (avoiding the holes), that shielding corresponds to an extrapolated range energy of about 11.6 MeV. Passing through the innermost 4, 3, 2, or 1 blades corresponds, respectively, to extrapolated range energies of 7.9, 6.0, 4.9, and 2.4 MeV. To estimate the most likely electron energies to contribute to the penetrating background, our conservative approach uses combinatorial mathematics to decide the probability of penetrating each level of shielding. Just to give a sense of what this process means, consider that there is one combination of impacts each that results in the electron penetrating either all 4 or none of the four innermost blades, but there are 4 and 6 combinations for penetrating 3 or 2 of those blades, respectively. The outermost blade is treated differently because it is twice as thick. We then convolved those derived probabilities with the shape of the penetrating electron distributions. Assuming a spectral shape of $1/E^\gamma$, (with total integral

flux for electrons with energy $> E$ with shape $1/E^{\gamma-1}$) and then using fairly high values of γ (2.5 to 2.0), we estimate that the range of energies contributing most to the penetrating background are conservatively >6 MeV electrons. A less conservative approach that examines different classes of trajectories, but does not consider all trajectories that have large angles to the normal (passing through more absorbing material), we estimate the range of energies contributing most to the penetrating background as >8 MeV. The directionality of JEDI's susceptibility to penetrating electron radiation is demonstrated well in an event studied by Mauk et al. (2024).

JEDI Witness Detectors. The so-called "witness" detectors (Mauk et al., 2017a) offers the most important indicator of side-penetrating electrons. Despite their deficiencies, discussed here, it is recommended that one of the first things to do in analyzing a segment of JEDI data is to plot out the witness detectors. These witness detectors are found in the data product designated as "Ion Energy Spectra" data from the JEDI sensor JEDI-A180 (the word "ion" is misleading because these nominally ion detectors are responding mostly to electrons). The small-pixel ion SSDs in the JEDI sensor JEDI-A180 serve the purpose described here, and for most of the mission, these sensors were commanded into the small pixel configuration, particularly close to the planet. Three of 6 of these pixels (telescopes T2, T4, and T5) are bare and measure foreground electrons with energies greater than about 20 keV. Two of the 6 pixels (telescopes T1 and T3) have thin shields covering them (0.64 mm titanium). According to the procedures of Tabata et al. (2002), these shields correspond to an electron extrapolated range (E_{extr}) of ~ 0.86 MeV, and a 99% blockage of about $0.7 \times E_{extr} = 0.6$ MeV. (Telescope "0" is bare but is partially blocked by a sun shield and is not used for these analyses; its response is typically between that of the shielded and unshielded detectors.)

In non-penetrating environments, the shielded and unshielded witness detectors show different responses. However, when the dominant inputs that these 6 telescopes are receiving are from electron radiation that penetrates detector shielding, all of the sensor see essentially the same output. The bottom panel of Figure S4 shows a characteristic example. This is just a plot of total summed counts received by each witness SSD (being careful not to include the very lowest energy channels, well below the energies required of JEDI, when those detectors are contaminated with detector noise; see Text S10, Item 11). Here, Juno is traveling in Jupiter's inner magnetosphere, moving inside of the Moon Io's L-shell. On the left of the figure, well outside of Io's orbit, telescopes T2, T4, and T5 are well separated from telescopes T1 and T3, indicating that fair foreground measurements are being made. That conclusion is reinforced by the observations in the 3rd panel of clear dynamic electron injection signatures. However, on the right side of the panel the 5 telescopes all pinch together, indicating that these sensors are all overwhelmed by shield penetrating electrons. Hence, the electron spectra shown in the 3rd panel of Figure S4 is judged to be fully contaminated in this region. Note that JEDI, designed to measure Jupiter polar phenomena that magnetically map to regions near and outside of Europa's orbit, was not designed to make measurements near Io's orbit. However, the ion measurements (2nd panel) are shown in the figure, somewhat off the

equator, are judged to be relatively clean, even while revealing some “accidentals” contamination in the lowest intensity regions (as discussed in Section S9).

We have several warnings about the use of the witness detectors. First, the process described here is only available when the JEDI-A180 ion SSDs are in their small pixel modes (That is the most likely orientation but there might be times when this is not the case). Second, because of scattering within the measurement volume of JEDI, the shielded witness detectors (T1 and T3) actually measure about 8% of the > 20 keV, non-penetrating foreground electrons. Quantitative use of the witness detectors must take this scattering component into account. For example, the maximum contrast between the shielded and unshielded detectors will be something like $8/100 = 0.08$. That contrast will be even smaller if there are substantial foreground electrons (those that enter properly through the collimator) with energies greater than those that penetrate the witness shields (MeV-class electrons), as is certainly the case shown in Figure S4.

The pitch angle structure can complicate these measurements. Specifically, over the poles, where even side-penetrating electrons can occur in the form of magnetic field-aligned beams, it is sometimes observed that the shielded detectors have even higher rates than do the unshielded detectors. This situation occurs when the orientation of the sensor is such that the beaming penetrating electrons come through the JEDI collimator and illuminate one of the shielded SSDs to a greater extent than they do the unshielded sensors. In strongly beaming situations, the witness detector system can be difficult to interpret. Note that the unique characteristics of the witness detectors can also be used to provide a scientific metric of the environment, as shown by Paranicas et al. (2018) in measurements over Jupiter’s poles.

There are other indicators of strongly penetrating electrons. As documented in Paranicas et al. (2017) and Kollmann et al. (2017), the presence of penetrators in a given energy channel can be identified in regions close enough to Jupiter to where JEDI resolves the loss cone. The upward loss cones should be relatively empty in the radiation belts unless the detectors are contaminated with side penetrators. Elsewhere and where the external distributions have non-isotropic pitch angle distributions, unnatural patterns emerge in the electron pitch angle distributions whenever side penetrators are playing a role. This issue is most important very close to Jupiter when Juno passes the horns of the hard radiation belts. Another indication of the importance of side penetrating electrons can be derived by applying the procedure documented in section S1. Even electrons with energies > 15 MeV will contribute to the generation of the minimum ionizing feature. The feature in the 3rd panel of Figure S4 labeled “e- penetrators” is the minimum ionizing signature of shield penetrating electrons.

Text S6. Electron angle resolution issues

Here we discuss issues that arise with the JEDI electron measurements when the features that are being observed are more structured in angle than can be resolved by the JEDI fields-of-view.

The instantaneous full-width-at-half-maximum field of view (FOV) of the JEDI electron telescopes is about $9^\circ \times 17^\circ$. The accumulation time for each high-rate sampling (the mode that JEDI always uses near the planet) is about 0.25 seconds occurring about every 0.5 seconds. The 0.5 second cadence corresponds to about 1/60 of a rotation, or about 6° of rotational motion, roughly in the direction that corresponds to the " 17° " dimension in the FOV. With accumulation times of about 0.25 seconds, the electron measurements are smeared in angle by about 3° along the 17° opening of the instantaneous FOV.

There are narrow angular beams that JEDI has observed, particularly in the upward direction over the polar cap (Mauk et al., 2017a; see Figure S5). JEDI does not resolve these beams. JEDI's derived intensities will be low for such beam for two different reasons. First, if one generates pitch angle distributions with resolution elements that are too coarse (e. g. 15 degrees), then some observations will be included in the field-aligned accumulations that do not have the magnetic field line contained within the FOV at any time during the accumulation. For the very narrow beams, one should utilize pitch angle resolutions in the plots as narrow as 4.5 degrees (half of the 9° FOV opening) to make sure that any accumulation purporting to be in the field-aligned direction actually includes the field line within the accumulation. For a 30 second accumulation (one spacecraft spin), the somewhat offset configuration of the JEDI viewing often allows resolutions down to 4.5 degrees. But there will also be time gaps. For shorter time accumulations it is unlikely that consistent viewing down to within 4.5 degrees of the field line can be achieved.

It has turned out to be very fortunate (and also physically significant in a way that we do not yet understand) that the downward going electron intensities over the main aurora are often much broader in angle than the upward going intensities in some main aurora regions. Various analyses have shown that often one may sometimes average over, say, 15 degrees without engendering substantial spin modulation in the downward fluxes. However, for the analysis of any particular period of time, the researcher must perform a number of different experimental tests with the data to make absolutely sure that there is not an angular sampling problem. Such experiments involve plotting and re-plotting the data using a variety of combinations of time resolution and angle resolution to see how the character of the plots changes. For example, does one get a sudden burst of energy flux only at the instance when the pitch angle coverage is particularly complete and not elsewhere?

Missing the field line is only one of the ways that intensities might be in error. The second reason that JEDI intensities of beams are a lower limit is this: when we convert count rates into intensities, we assume that the FOV of the instrument is uniformly filled. For narrow beams, such as the upward beams over the poles, the FOV is not filled

because JEDI does not resolve the beams. Under this circumstance the apparent intensities and energy fluxes will be lower than they should be. No correction has been applied to the JEDI data to mitigate these occurrences.

Text S7. Electron internal scattering

Here we discuss the issues that arise with the JEDI electron measurements as a result of electron scattering within the JEDI sensor volume.

One of the driving requirements for the JEDI instrument was to be able to obtain nearly complete pitch angle distributions at every instant of time (0.5 second distributions). Because of the rapid motion of the spacecraft (up to 55 km/s) and the slow rotation of the spacecraft (2 rotations per minute), a multiplicity of simultaneous look directions is required. To obtain the needed number of look directions using limited resources, we chose to allow the trajectories of the particles to share a common sensor volume (Mauk et al., 2017a). When electrons enter the sensor volume of JEDI, some of them can hit internal structures within the sensor other than the SSDs. A fraction of those electrons can scatter and find their way to other SSDs from directions that were not intended with the sensor design. This mechanism limits the contrast that can be seen within highly structured features, such as strongly magnetic field aligned beams. Figure S5 shows some example electron pitch angle distributions (30 – 1000 keV) that reveal the character of scattered component. These are measurements of very narrow, magnetic field-aligned electron beams within Jupiter's polar caps (Mauk et al., 2017b). The left-hand plots show that the scattered component exists at something like the percent level. However, an aspect of the response that requires special vigilance is the situation where the electron beam enters the detector from a direction that is not quite ideal; that is the center of the angular beam does not hit the center of the SSD. Rather, parts of the beam are aimed at structures that are off to the side of the SSD. In these cases, the contrast between the measured beam and the scattered component can be less than the 1% mentioned above. For example, the plot on the right of Figure S5 shows a contrast (signal to noise) at the 5-10% level. Such low signal-to-noise situations can happen when JEDI does not angularly resolve the features of interest (see also Text S6). Much care must be exercised in analyzing these very narrow features.

Text S8. Contamination of electrons by protons.

A 2-micron aluminum flashing covers the entrance surface of the electron SSDs. This flashing is intended to protect the electron detectors from proton contamination. It also limits the electron SSD response to electrons with energies greater than about 25 keV. But, protons with energies greater than about 300 keV can contaminate the electron measurements. Such contamination is rare up to energies where electrons are efficiently measured (energies less than 1-2 MeV) because typically the electrons are much more intense than are the ions. One such rare contamination example from the magnetosphere is shown in Figure S6. On the other hand, proton contamination of

electrons can be common for the region of the innermost radiation belt (Kollmann et al., 2017).

Use Table S1 to compute the level of contamination. One compares the intensity of the protons (that is measured without ambiguity through the TOFxE coincidence) at the energy in the first column with the nominal electron intensity at the energy of the middle column (with the Equation 1 efficiency factor not applied, or removed if already applied). That middle column energy is the energy that a proton will have after it penetrates the aluminum flashing and the several very thin foils that the proton encounters prior to encountering the flashing. If the electron channel intensity (again, absent the Equation 1 efficiency) is much larger than the proton intensity for that pair of energies, then there is little or no contamination of the electrons by the protons. If the intensity numbers are close, then some proton contamination of the electrons is likely. Formally, it is the Phase Space Densities (PSD) at the pair of energies ($PSD = \text{Intensity}/p^2$, where p is momentum) that should be compared, but that correction would likely be too small to matter for this crude comparison.

Note that the most recent onboard tables (see Text S10, Item 3) increased the energies of the highest electron energy channels to values close to 10 MeV. Because the efficiency of electron detection drops so rapidly with energy (Equations 1), it is highly likely (unless proven otherwise) that energies substantially higher than 1 MeV will be contaminated by protons or ions.

Text S9. “Accidental” contamination of ion measurements.

Ions are measured with a coincidence system. For the low energy “time-of-flight by pulse height” (TOFxPH) measurements, a valid event is one that has both a “start” generated by electrons coming out of a “start foil”, with secondary electrons striking portions of the JEDI microchannel plate (MCP); and a “stop” generated by electrons coming out of a “stop foil” with secondary electrons striking another portion of the MCP (see Figure 11 in Mauk et al., 2017a). The “start” and “stop” must both occur within a time window of no greater than about 150 ns, the longest relevant time-of-flight for the JEDI measurements. For a higher energy “time-of-flight by energy” (TOFxE) measurement an additional 3rd signal is required within an additional time window, a signal from one of the solid-state-detectors (SSDs). The time window for that 3rd signal to occur with respect to the time-of-flight signals is about 280-330 ns, a range that results from an uncertainty in our present knowledge (see later discussion). Both of these measurements (TOFxPH and TOFxE) are immune to low levels of penetrating electrons because any one such electron can (generally) stimulate only one of the two or three needed signals.

However, once either the penetrating electrons become overwhelming, or the system is overdriven even by non-penetrating particles (electrons or ions), the required multiple signals can be stimulated by separate, randomly occurring particles within the time windows specified in the preceding paragraph. The result is contamination of the

measurements called “accidentals”. Such contamination, for example, is apparent in the right-hand-side of the proton measurements of Figure S4 (Panel b) with features labeled “e-”. And in the same region, the top panel of Figure S4 shows a region of heavy ion measurements that are fully contaminated with accidentals caused by electrons. These types of contaminations are particularly severe within the horns of the electron radiation belts over the poles. In Figure S7 (Figure 3 of Mauk et al.; 2017b), an apparent entire false proton population is created by accidentals (second from the bottom panel); observed between 1220 and 1235m and between 1300 and 1320. Note that TOF_xPH data, with only 2 coincident signals, is particularly sensitive to accidental contamination. That is one reason why the TOF_xPH data is under-utilized in JEDI publications.

One of the difficulties in evaluating accidental contamination with JEDI is that the instrument reports on total start rates ($R[\text{start}]$) and total stop rates ($R[\text{stop}]$) of all of the telescopes combined, whereas the accidental contamination is dependent on the start and stop rates within each telescope. $R[\text{start}]$ and $R[\text{stop}]$ are reported in the TOF data files. Because the instrument is almost always set to demand that start sectors (1 of 6) and stop sectors (1 of 6) must match each other, the telescopes act independently with regard to accidental rates. We use the designations $RD[\text{start}]$ and $RD[\text{stop}]$ to indicate the “directional” start and stop rates. But, the RDs are not reported by the instrument. If we believe that that the particles that are causing the contamination are isotropic (striking all telescopes roughly equally), then we would set $RD[\text{start}] = R[\text{start}]/6$ and $RD[\text{stop}] = R[\text{stop}]/6$, which may often be nearly valid within Jupiter’s near the magnetic equator, at least outside of Io. But, if the contaminating events are highly directional (as they can be over the aurora and over the polar cap) then some other choice is needed. A worst-case selection would be $RD[\text{start}] = R[\text{start}]$ and $RD[\text{stop}] = R[\text{stop}]$. Within nominally isotropic regions that may have some angular structure within the contaminating populations, a conservative approach might use $RD[\text{start}] = R[\text{start}]/3$ and $RD[\text{stop}] = R[\text{stop}]/3$.

TOF_xPH Data

For TOF_xPH data, we are focusing on proton channels only, since the large effort needed to quantify the heavy ion TOF_xPH channels has not yet been performed (see Text S10, Item 19). The rate of accidentals contaminating a TOF_xPH energy channel for a specific telescope is the rate of directional start events ($RD[\text{start}]$) times the probability of a random (uncorrelated) stop event occurring within the relevant time window ($RD[\text{stop}]$). The relevant time window depends on the goal that we are trying to achieve. If we are looking for any contamination within the entirety of the TOF_xPH measurements, we need to use the longest acceptable TOF, 150ns. Usually however we are interested in the accidentals within a given energy range that is established by a range of TOFs. In that case the window for an individual energy channel is t_2-t_1 , where t_2 and t_1 are the TOFs that correspond to the low and high energy boundaries of that particular channel. Tables S2 and S3 can be used to estimate these respective times. Table S2 provides the coefficients of 6th order polynomial fits to the TOF versus input energy for each mass species. Table S3 shows some calculated values from those polynomial fits (some

nonsense numbers occur outside of the nominal energy ranges of the sensors). The range of allowed input energies for each channel can be taken from the column labels of the Level 3 data.

The rate of accidental TOF_xPH contamination for a give energy channel for any specific telescope (call it RD1) is:

$$RD1[\text{accidental}] = RD[\text{start}] \times \{1 - \text{Exp}[-RD[\text{stop}] \times (t_2 - t_1)]\} \quad (7)$$

Here, the exponential factor is the Poisson probability of getting zero counts within the time window. Hence, one (1) minus the exponential is the probability of getting one or more counts within the time window. When $RD \times (t_2 - t_1) < 1$ one can expand the exponential and keep only the first two terms in that expansion, yielding the commonly used form (Eckart and Shonka, 1938):

$$RD1[\text{accidental}] = RD[\text{start}] \times RD[\text{stop}] \times (t_2 - t_1) \quad (8)$$

And again, $RD[\text{start}]$ and $RD[\text{stop}]$ are not reported by the instrument. As indicated near the beginning of this section, one must decide on the “ n ” and “ m ” of the equations $RD[\text{start}] = R[\text{start}]/n$ and $RD[\text{stop}] = R[\text{stop}]/m$, where “ n ” and “ m ” can each range between 1 and 6. The final parameter of interest is “ $n \times m$ ”, which can range from 1 (for unrealistically extreme directional background), to a theoretical value of 36 for isotropic background. Because the detector shielding is directional (Text S5), the highest value expected in practice seems to be 25. A reasonably conservative choice for broad distributions might be 10.

Fortunately, for TOF_xPH proton data, it is often unnecessary to do this kind of detailed calculation. For this proton data product, accidentals yield a universal spectrum that is very easy to identify, as can be seen in Figure S8 (from Mauk et al., 2023). For JEDI High Energy Resolution TOF_xPH proton data (with the particular channel designations used with that data product), that spectrum, expressed as an intensity versus energy, is approximated with the following polynomial form, again for protons:

$$\text{Log}_{10}[I_{\text{acc}}/C] = -1.9345 \times LE^3 + 9.9785 \times LE^2 - 18.9779 \times LE + 13.3799 \quad (9)$$

where I_{acc} is the accidentals intensity ($1/[\text{cm}^2 \text{ s sr keV}]$), C is a normalizing constant, $LE = \text{Log}_{10}(E_{\text{keV}})$, and E_{keV} is energy in keV. This expression was derived using $(\Delta t / (\epsilon \Delta E))$ where Δt is the time difference associated with the high and low energy bounds of each channel expressed in nano-sec (ns), ϵ is measurement efficiency for real protons, and ΔE is the energy band width for each channel in units of keV. Note again that this expression is only for the JEDI High-Energy-Resolution data and is strongly dependent on the exact definitions of the energy channels.

The procedure to testing the presence of accidentals is to vary the C and see if the low energy portion of the spectrum matches the accidentals spectrum shape, a shape that is often unlikely to be reproduced by natural events. That condition is seen to be true in Figure S8. We note also that the efficiency for the detection of true signal H+ between 5 and 10 keV is so low that any counts that exist within that energy range may represent a signature that accidental counts are present (as found in the examples explored by Mauk et al., 2023).

Formally the "C" parameter in Equation (9) is $= RD[start]*RD[stop]*(1E-9)/G$, where the geometric factor G is roughly $2.8E-3$ (Text S10 Item 23) and RD[start] and RD[stop] are rates expressed as 1/sec. Using this factor, one may explore quantitative contamination factors in addition to just exploring the shape of the contamination spectrum, as described in the preceding paragraph. The game is to explore different values of "n x m" as described just under Equation (8).

TOFxE data

Accidental contamination is strongly suppressed if the solid-state detectors are stimulated (representing the TOFxE data product). And so, one of the first things to do in assessing accidental contamination in the TOFxE data is to check whether the higher energy TOFxPH channels are contaminated using the technique described in the previous paragraphs. If those higher energy TOFxPH channels are uncontaminated, then the TOFxE data for the same look directions are also certainly uncontaminated. But, if TOFxPH is fully contaminated as it can be close to the planet, more effort will be required.

By adding the 3rd signal from the SSDs, one obtains (call it RD2):

$$RD2[accidental] = RSSD[\Delta E] \times TSSD \times RD[start] \times RD[stop] \times (t2-t1) \quad (10)$$

where again, Poisson exponentials (like that in Equation 7) are expanded and truncated to yield the results shown here. Here, RSSD[ΔE] is the raw counts measured by the relevant directional SSD within the relevant energy band, and TSSD is the SSD coincidence time for identifying an event. RSSD[ΔE] is not provided within the TOFxE data product, and estimates of this parameter must be found elsewhere (see the next paragraph). Formally the SSD integration time (TSSD) is something like 430 ns (mode dependent), but empirically we have found that a coincidence time like 280 ns is needed in the equation for TSSD above to give the accidental rates that we see in data like that presented in Figure S4 (top). The small difference between formal and empirical value makes sense because Eq. 10 assumes a simplified coincidence scheme, in which a valid coincidence requires the start signal to occur before the stop signal, and the stop signal before the SSD signal. An SSD signal occurring within the start-stop interval does not veto the coincidence. In practice, the pulse ordering for valid coincidences is less well defined because of electronic delays and clock jitter. An SSD pulse arriving 20 ns before the Stop pulse may still be identified as a valid coincidence in about 90% of cases. When

the SSD pulse arrives 80 ns before the Stop pulse, the event is typically classified as invalid instead. Eq. 10 does not capture these details exactly, but it is still able to fit the observations when using an empirically chosen value of TSSD.

It is non-trivial to estimate $RSSD[\Delta E]$. To do so, energy-resolved SSD rates are needed through the "ion spectra" and/or "electron spectra" products (not the TOF data products). These products may be available for the same JEDI unit; otherwise, a neighboring JEDI will need to be used (with uncertainties associated with the directionality of the contaminating events). Important here is that the SSD-only energy channel(s) selected need to be associated with the same range of energies as that deposited in association with the TOFxE channel of interest. Tables S4 and S5 provide the needed conversions. For example, if one is looking for the accidental rates in an Oxygen channel with an energy range of E1 to E2, one would look for the range of energies involved with that channel in the second to the last column in Table S5. Then, under the assumption that electrons (penetrating or not) are responsible for most of the starts and stops, and if one is using a bare detector, like the uncovered witness detectors (JEDI-A180 "ion energy spectra"), one would use the count rates in those witness detectors interpolated and summed over the range of energies in the left-hand column for those detectors to estimate $RSSD[\Delta E]$. Interpolation and perhaps summation is needed because the witness detector energy channels are unlikely to match the needed range of energies. If one uses the electron detectors rather than bare witness detectors, one would obtain the needed range of energies from the 3rd column of Table S4 rather than from the left-hand column. And, if the TOFxE measurement uses large SSD pixels (as it almost always does) and the Witness Detectors or other detectors that make use of small pixels, the estimated $RSSD[\Delta E]$ would have to be scaled up by a factor of something like 14 (See Text S10, Item 24).

Note that the "Deposited Energy" in Tables S4 and S5 is not the same as the "Measured Energy" for the ions. The Measured Energy must include an additional "Pulse Height Defect" associated with the measurement of heavy ions. Tables S4 and S5 work for the purposes of this section under the assumption that the Starts and Stops that cause the accidental contamination are created by electrons. For electrons, the Deposited and Measured energies are the same.

Again, this entire process is non-trivial and not for the faint-at-heart. Note that channel rates (in addition to channel intensities) are reported by the instrument (see Text S10, Item 7). Note also that it is the R vs. R corrected rates that one needs to use in these evaluations. This complicated process was used to obtain the red dashed line in the top panel of Figure S4. For that figure the derived accidental rates were then turned into an equivalent intensity value. That conversion is an unnecessary step for just deciding whether or not the measurements are contaminated. After deriving accidental rates (RD1 for TOFxPH or RD2 for TOFxE) for a given energy channel, one then compares them with the rates that are reported by the instruments for each of those TOF-data energy

channels. Again, the needed R vs. R channel rates are reported by the instrument (see Text S10 Item 7)

Text S10. Miscellanea

1. JEDI Data Products. JEDI contains many data products, some of which were invented to fit JEDI data within limited data volumes. For each of the 3 JEDI sensors (J90, J270, J180) there are data products for Low Energy Resolution Electrons, High Energy Resolution Electrons, Low Energy Resolution time-of-flight x energy protons (TOFxE), High Energy Resolution TOFxE protons, Non-Proton TOFxE Heavy Ions, Low Energy Resolution time-of-flight x pulse-height protons (TOFxPH), High Energy Resolution TOFxPH protons, Non-Proton TOFxPH Heavy Ions, Low Energy Resolution "Ion" Spectra (usually dominated by electrons), and High Energy Resolution "Ion" Spectra (also usually dominated by electrons). The Witness Detectors are found in the JEDI-A180 "Ion" Spectra Data Products, but are useful as witness detectors only when the ion sensors are in small pixel mode. Because of problems with high voltage on JEDI-A180, TOF data is not taken on that unit. Also, during the extended mission during September of 2022 (about perijove 45), the high voltage on JEDI-90 also failed, eliminating TOF data products from that unit. A reliable way to determine which data products are available at any one time is to go to: <http://sd-www.jhuapl.edu/jedi/data/webapp/>. There one may set a date, a JEDI unit, and select "DATA_PRESENT". This web site is also very useful for getting a summary about how the JEDI units are responding to the jovian environment. With the generation of any particular data product described here, there are parameters that can be set to adjust data volume. These parameters include time resolutions, sector averaging (out of the nominal 60 sectors per spin), and even multiple spin averaging.
2. JEDI True Ion Data Products. True ion data are found ONLY in the data products whose file names contain the acronym "TOF". The data products with the word "Ion" in them are usually dominated by electrons. These "ion" data products contain the word "ion" only because they come from the SSD's that are used to measure ions with the coincident TOF process.
3. An Important Onboard Table Change. During Day 110 in 2024, a new set of onboard tables was uploaded to the JEDI instrument with the intent of increasing the energy resolution of heavy ions at the expense of proton energy resolution. Designated Tables V4, this change is in addition to the several other onboard table changes documented in Text S10 Item 13 below. We document this change separately because it can lead to substantial confusion. Because of various constraints on this process (technical and programmatic), we chose to swap the High- and Low- Energy Resolution TOFxE data files (which up to this time contained only protons) with the Non-Proton TOFxE data files (which up to this time contained only heavy ions). That is: following the date given at the beginning of this paragraph, the Non-Proton-TOFxE contain only protons and helium ions (despite the file name), and the High- and Low- Energy Resolution TOFxE data contain only heavy ions. However, the

channel labels within each data file are correct and can be relied upon to identify the correct species and the correct energy range for that species.

4. JEDI Energy Channel Range Variations. The energy channels of the three JEDI instruments do not exactly match each other because of the variations in the responses of different solid-state detectors (SSD). Within each instrument there was a major effort to choose SSDs that matched each other in their responses (small differences remain). But between the different instruments there are noticeable differences. In order to plot combined spectra, some resampling is necessary. In the software that is internal to the JEDI team for plotting, one may choose native bins (which can give some choppy looking spectra because of the channel mismatches), "fuzzy bins" that resamples to generate a compromise between the channels of the multiple units, or completely resampled logarithmically spaced bins.
5. Effect of Strong Magnetic Fields. In the very strong magnetic field close to Jupiter, the size of the spacecraft is comparable to the electron gyro-radii. This causes the spacecraft to shadow observations of the electrons. The effect is complicated, but the zero-order effect of this shadowing is a minimum in the apparent intensity of electrons near pitch angles of 90° . A labeled example of this effect can be found in Figure 8 of Mauk et al., (2020).
6. High Energy Electron Efficiency Application. While we have no automated process for doing the full correction on the JEDI electron data as described in Text S1, we did decide mid-mission to start applying the high energy tail correction (Equation (1)) to the archived JEDI data. The data files (in the form of ASCII) generated since we started doing this correction as part of the processing have a keyword EFFCOR in the up-front meta data. If that parameter is set to T, the correction has already been applied. If it is set to F, or if that keyword is missing completely, the correction was not applied. This is a reliable way to know for sure whether the high energy tail was corrected on a file-by-file basis. Our difficulty in automating a full correction of the data (high energy tail and eliminating the minimum ionizing peak) arose when the process continued to have difficulty in distinguishing electrostatic auroral acceleration from the minimum ionizing feature. More effort than we had available is needed to resolve this issue.
7. Data Product Contents. Three parameters are reported for each energy channel: i) counts per accumulation, ii) counts per second, and iii) differential number Intensity. The counts per accumulation are raw counts, uncorrected by any knowledge of the response of the instrument to inputs. It can be used to assess statistical significance. It can be turned into a counts per second by dividing by the "duration" time (which usually is shorter than the interval between adjacent measurements due to multiplexing), also provided in the up-front information within each record. The recorded counts per second have had corrections applied to it to take into account the limitations in the instrument for counting particles (so-called "R versus R" corrections; see Text S4). The Intensity is calculated on the basis of this corrected counts per second. Note that the raw counts divided by duration will not match the

recorded counts per second because of the corrections. When determining the statistical significance of a channel intensity averaged over time, it is important to remember to sum the counts per accumulation rather than to average them. Pitch angle information, spacecraft position relative to the jovian system, and look directions in a joviacentric coordinate systems are also included in the data files.

8. Onboard Energy Determinations. For SSD measurements, particle energy is measured on the basis of solid-state-detector (SSD) pulses using two different techniques. Up to about 1.5 MeV the energy is measured on the basis of the height of the SSD pulses. Above about 1.5 MeV the energy is measured on the basis of the time-width of the pulses. This two-technique approach substantially increases the dynamic range for the measurements. However, the energy derived from the high energy pulse-width measurements is, as of this writing, less consistent between the different units, and overall is less calibrated than are the pulse height measurements. While still imperfect, recent versions of the calibration matrices infer the higher energy ambient particle energies in such cases using the Time-of-Flight values rather than the SSD pulse widths.
9. Low Energy Limitations. For electrons with energies less than 30 keV, protons with energies less than 50 keV, and heavy ions less than 150 keV, the detector discrimination levels affect the efficiency of detection. As of this date, the intensities below these respective energies are uncalibrated, and provide intensities below (but sometimes above) the true values. At some point in time, effort may be expended to calibrate the channels below those energies.
10. Angular Resolution. The Full-Width-at-Half Maximum (FWHM) angular resolution of the JEDI TOFxE and electron measurements is roughly $9^\circ \times 17^\circ$, with the 17° oriented along the 160° JEDI field-of-view. The TOFxPH data is not geometrically constrained by the SSDs, and its FWHM angular resolution is closer to $9^\circ \times 30^\circ$.
11. SSD Aging Item 1. As the SSDs age with use and radiation, their noise levels at very low energies increase. We generally try to set detector signal thresholds to exclude this noise. However, sometimes we get behind in raising thresholds with the result that the very lowest energy channels have substantial false counts in them. To this date, the energy channels affected by detector noise have energies far below the energy measurements required of JEDI. That is, for electrons, the energy of the noise levels is far below 25 keV. Because of coincidence circuitry, the detector noise (always at fairly low values) does not affect the TOF ion measurements.
12. SSD Aging Item 2. In addition to becoming noisy at the very lowest energies (item 11 above), another consequence of radiation forcing on SSDs is a minor loss of sensitivity. This loss of sensitivity causes the time-of-flight (TOF) x Energy (E) tracks to migrate to lower energies. Because the channelization of the ions into different species (H, He, O, S) are fixed at any one time based on the TOFxE characteristics, such migrations can cause different ion species to mix together in the data channels. In particular, sometimes the S track will have migrated partially into the O bins). This process is one of the reasons that onboard look-up tables are periodically updated.

These migrations are diagnosed with a Level-2 data product called "Raw Ion Species Event" data which captures a small sampling of TOFxE particle events. These events are displayed on a Time-of-Flight versus Energy display and where onboard channels can be overlaid.

13. Table Changes Over Time. Over the life of the mission, changes have been made to the on-board tables that modify the energy channels sampled (v0, v1, v2, v3, v4, to date). The beginning dates of each of the (so far) five tables are: 2011-Day235 (Table v0z), 2015-Day104 (Table v1L), 2016-Day236 (Table v2f), 2019-Day127 (Table v3b), and 2024-Day111 (Table v4.14). The letters at the ends of the earlier Table names track modifications to the calibration matrices used to process the data generated by these onboard tables. The updating process changed in generating v4 so that that naming contains a version number for the calibration matrices that process these data (originally version 14). All of the calibration matrices used to process the data generated by these tables are being updated based on improved understanding achieved over the life of the mission so far. The working matrices have recently become v0af, v1r, v2An, v2Bn, v3j, and v4.17. Here the original v2 matrices have been split into v2A and v2B, with v2B beginning on Day 1, 2017. One of the key changes for the most recent onboard table update (v4) was to increase the energies that are sampled in the highest energy ion and electron channels. There will be more table changes to come. Note that data generated before 21 January 2026 was generated using early versions of the calibration matrices. Eventually we hope to regenerate all of the JEDI data using updated matrices.
14. Occasional High Voltage Disruptions. Occasionally, the high voltages on JEDI-90 and JEDI-270 trip off due to what are described as "micro-discharges" within the system. JEDI electronics senses these micro-discharges and commands the HV off just to make sure that the sensors are not damaged. True ions are not measured when the HV is off. While early in the mission these events required ground commands to restore the HV on the affected unit, presently the HV is turned on automatically after 12 hours, originally, and 6 hours presently.
15. High Voltage Issues and SSD damage. As a result of the failure of the JEDI-A180 high voltage early in the mission, and the failure of the JEDI-90 high voltage during the extended mission (September 2022), one of the 24 SSD electronic chains on each of these instruments was damaged. (Note that there are 6 large electron SSD pixels, 6 small electron SSD pixels, 6 large ion SSD pixels, and 6 small SSD pixels, for a total of 24). On JEDI-A180, the SSD pixel electronics that was damage is the Large Ion Pixel for Telescope #5. Because we use the ion SSDs on JEDI-A180 in the Small Pixel configuration (as our Witness Detectors), this damaged SSD pixel is almost never used. However, on JEDI-90, with the failure first noted in April of 2023 (during an attempt to bring the HV back on line and just before Jupiter perijove 51), it was the Large Electron Pixel on Telescope #0 that failed. The Large Electron Pixels on JEDI-90 are the ones that are nominally used, and so the user must be careful not to utilize Electron Telescope #0 on that instrument.

16. MCP Count Rate Protection. There is one additional HV safety alarm feature: when the micro-channel plate count rates rise above a (settable) threshold (on average over each 30 second spin), the HV is reduced to a low value. Originally, operational HV is restored the next time the HV is exercised on the spacecraft, typically during a spacecraft thrusting activity, which happens fairly often to maintain the spacecraft orientation. JEDI HV are turned down during these thrusting activities. However, more recently the HV is automatically reset (following a count rate alarm) after a set time lag, presently 5 minutes.
17. Heavy Ion Discrimination. JEDI does not discriminate between Oxygen (O) and Sulfur (S) at energies below about 600 keV, with the exact value dependent on the onboard tables. Below that energy the O and S counts are combined (with intensities calculated as if these ions were oxygen, assuming a 1:1 mixture that is roughly consistent with what is typically observed at higher, mass-resolved energies). Above that energy there are separate O and S channels.
18. TOFPH Proton Data Challenges. There are several issues of which one must be aware in using the low energy TOFPH proton data. First, as discussed in Section S9, it is highly susceptible to accidental contamination. Second, the efficiency of detection decreases substantially with decreasing energy, as can be seen by comparing the "Intensity" and "Counts" profiles in Figure S8. Sometimes a distribution on a spectrogram will look like an energy beam, whereas the truth is that the instrument just ran out of counts at the lower energies. Additionally, the energy resolution decreases with decreasing energy, as seen in Figure 34 of Mauk et al. (2017a). A final "feature" of the TOFPH measurements is that there is a changeable multiplicative "decimation" factor that limits the number of TOFPH events that are processed in order to prevent TOFPH data from overwhelming the onboard event processing. Various values have been used, but a decimation factor of 4 has been found to provide a nice balance between TOFPH and TOFxE event processing. A decimation factor of 4 means that only every 4th TOFPH event is processed by the onboard computer.
19. TOFPH Heavy Ion Data Challenges. The heavy ion channels that are a part of the TOFPH data have not been quantified, and much work remains to be done. Further work may in fact find that this data is not useful. In order to prevent proton contamination, the onboard table channels for the heavy ions "throw away" the vast majority of heavy ions events because there are no channels assigned to the region in TOFPH space where the proton and heavy ion populations blur into each other. The fraction of heavy ions retained depends strongly on the microchannel plate (MCP) gains at the time of the measurement, and is typically a very (very) small fraction of the total. While a multiplication factor can be generated by comparing TOFPH and TOFxE intensities where they cross over at near 200 keV, the energy dependence of the "throw-away" process needs to be determined. A very rough estimate (derived with a comparison with JADE at about 45 keV on 2019; Day 95; 1700 to 2130) has an additional energy-graduated reduction reaching about a factor of 3 near 50 keV using an expression like: Corrected-Intensity = Raw-Intensity x 10^{^(-}

0.648 (2.389-Log10(E-keV)); this expression has Corrected-Intensity = Raw-Intensity at E=245 keV. The reader may be familiar with the Mitchell et al. (2003, 2004) use of pulse height to determine heavy ion composition with the Cassini MIMI instrument and the IMAGE HENA instruments. Those instruments measured pulse height associated with secondary electrons coming from direct hits on the MCP adding to those from a separate foil. With JEDI, pulse height comes from secondary electrons coming off of a single foil, a configuration that is less efficacious for this purpose.

20. Data Corruption from Radiation. Starting with perijoves PJ42, PJ46, PJ47, PJ48, and many perijoves beyond) we sometimes find corrupted spikes of data with count rates very different than are physically possible from the instrument. Because these spikes occur close to perijove, but sometimes prior to the encounter of hard radiation, our working hypotheses is that these spikes are radiation-induced corruptions that occur after the data is transferred to the spacecraft mass memory and before the data is transmitted to Earth. It is important, at the highest time resolution, to filter out any such spikes with count rates higher than $5E6$ [TBR] counts per second. Because of onboard compression, it is best to remove an entire spectrum when one of the channels is corrupted rather than just removing the specific channel in question. It is, of course, possible that some corruption could be at a level that is not filterable with such a simple algorithm. It does not suffice to filter time-averaged data because the anomalous high rates get averaged together with much lower rates. The known corruptions are most readily identified in moments of the distributions (e. g. energy-integrated number intensity) where even a single bad channel input can generate unphysical results. At some point in time, once the corruptions are better understood, the archived Level-3 data will be filtered. Note that the corruption sometimes occurs within the header and/or timing information of a data file. In such cases, hands-on corrections are required to restore the data, if restoration is at all possible. Because of these mechanisms, some data blocks can be permanently lost.
21. Species Identification for "Ion" SSD Energy Spectra. The "Ion Energy Spectra" data (files that do not have "TOF" in the file names) are most often dominated by electrons. Calibration matrices utilized for later portions of the mission have made that assumption so that the intensities provided are those of the presumed electrons. The individual channel labels let the user know when either protons or electrons were assumed. When electrons are assumed, care must be exercised to make sure that these detectors are not dominated by ions by comparing bare-detector-derived intensities (with the high energy electron efficiency factor--Equation 1--removed) with the TOFxE proton intensities. Here, Table S1 is not needed because the bare detectors do not have AI flashing on them (see Text S8).
22. An Issue with an SEU Evaluation Mode. During a portion of the mission so far, specifically between Perijove 20 (PJ20; Day 194, 2019) and Perijove 33 (Day 105, 2021) a special mode was introduced to assess the occurrence of Single Event Upsets (SEUs). This special mode had the unintended consequence of introducing periodic spikes in the data when the count rates were very high close to the planet, and most commonly in the non-targeted hard radiation regions. The spikes occur in the hard

radiation regions because it is there where the events fully utilize the capabilities of the onboard computer. Figure S10 shows what those spikes can look like in the JEDI online survey plots (<http://sd-www.jhuapl.edu/jedi/data/webapp/>). After those spikes were recognized, the cadence for implementing the SEU mode was drastically changed to once per orbit. By the way, no SEUs have been observed at any time as of this writing.

23. Update on JEDI Geometric Factors. Recently, a full GEANT4 simulation of the complicated JEDI response to external particle distributions (Zhu et al., 2025) revealed that the geometric factors used in standard processing were in error by up to almost a factor of 2 for both electrons and ions. That factor of 2 includes unmodeled contributions of foil-mounted screens and estimated solid-state-detector edge effects. Correction of this error reduces the derived intensities by that factor of 2. That correction is needed for any data generated before 21 January 2026. In addition, while making this correction the JEDI team also made the effort to re-evaluate the “flat fielding” of the multiple sensors, which adjusts the geometric factors of one telescope with respect to the others. Table S6 shows all of the newly corrected geometric factors and also provides information about individual telescopes. These new factors are being applied to all data generated after 21 January 2026 (whether that data was taken long ago or in the future). An estimate of the needed correction comes from applying the factor of almost 2 to reduce the derived electron and ion intensities. Note that particle intensities are derived by applying both the geometric factors shown in Tables S6 and also energy-dependent efficiencies of detection (not provided here). Efficiency curves may be extracted using (for each channel): $\text{Efficiency} = \text{Rate}(1/\text{s}) / [\text{Intensity} \times G \times (E2 - E1)]$, where “Rate(1/s)” are the corrected count rates reported in the Level 3 data, “Intensity” are the differential intensity values also reported in the Level 3 data, G is the Geometric Factors (Table S6, or earlier versions for earlier data), and {E2-E1} is the difference between the high and low energy boundaries of the energy channel. For ions, the microchannel plate (MCP) efficiencies discussed in Text S10 Item 25 are just one part of these efficiency curves.
24. Evaluation of the Quantitative Fidelity of the Small Electron Pixels. Detailed comparisons between the responses of electron Large Pixels and electron Small Pixels, in relatively homogeneous and isotropic environments, revealed non-linearities in the responses of the Small Pixels. While the Small Pixels are useful for qualitative analysis, their use for quantitative analyses has limitations. Figure S9 shows some of the uncertainties in using the electron Small Pixels for quantitative analysis. Shown are ratios between the response of Large and Small electron pixels in varying environment (R between 10 and 18 RJ near the magnetic equator). The dark solid line in the top panel, converted to an effective Small Pixel efficiency in the bottom panel, shows what we have chosen to use in converting Small Pixel Rates into Intensities, favoring to some extent the less non-linear responses observed beyond 15 RJ at the equator. The variations in the response depending on measurement location (evident in the top panel of Fig. S9) become much larger as one moves

further into the harder radiation closer to the planet, where the witness detectors suggest the presence of strong penetration electrons. Perijoves 34, 35, and 36 provide the best data for making these comparisons given the configurations of large and small pixels. Visual representations of when and where Large and Small Pixels were utilized can be found in the “Basic Rates” panels in <http://sd-www.jhuapl.edu/jedi/data/webapp/>. It should not be too surprising that anomalous behavior occurs as the sizes of the small pixels are only about a factor of 3 greater than their thicknesses.

25. MCP Gain Variations and Evaluation. Absolute detection efficiencies of particles passing the start and stop foils and causing a signal in the JEDI Microchannel Plates (MCPs) have uncertainties. JEDI transmits a special data product to ascertain these efficiencies. It is the “Level 2 Ion Energy Event” data. Each record of these files records a solid-state-detector (SSD) single particle event providing the deposition energy and whether or not that event had an associate MCP start pulse and/or MCP stop pulse. Selecting for events at energies near the peak of the proton dE/dX curve in carbon (70-90 keV), the equation in Figure 42 of Mauk et al., 2017 is used to derive start and stop MCP efficiencies at those energies. Total efficiency at that peak is then the product of those two numbers. For other energies and species, it is assumed that efficiencies scale according to the stopping power (dE/dX). The uncertainties arise when we are unsure of the composition of the ions coming in. Composition studies provided by Mauk et al. (2004) suggests regions where the analyses should be performed, but we have found that heavy ion contamination is likely more prevalent than expected in these regions. Electrons can also contaminate the results. Figure S11 provides a comprehensive look at the total calculated efficiencies over the life of the mission. Following the beginning of 2017 we believe that the true proton efficiencies are close to 0.3, with the large deviations above that value being due to heavy ion contamination, and the occasional low values due to electron contamination. Efficiencies derived in Figure S11 are being used as a part of the updating of the JEDI data processing. Total efficiency values used in generating data generated prior to 21 January 2026 used efficiencies about 24% lower than those shown in Figure S11 (prior to 2017), and about 24% higher after the beginning of 2017.

Text S11. References

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Figure S1. Electron differential number intensity energy spectra sampled by the JEDI instrument (blue symbols) used to describe a procedure for correcting the spectra when contaminated by penetrating electrons (panels A and B), testing the degree of such contamination when the detector is seeing coherent auroral acceleration (panel C), and testing whether or not the JEDI sensor is partially saturated (panel D). Blue symbols are the JEDI channel measurements, blue lines are the fits to the measurements (Equation 5) and red lines are the modeled incoming electron spectra (Equation 3). See the text for details.

Figure S2. Low and high limit to the auroral energy flux, as described in Text S2

Figure S3. Demonstration that SSD signal processes saturates at a level just above about 10^6 Counts per second. Here the counts of a small pixel measurement are compared to that of a large pixel. These rates roughly track each other until the large pixels rise above 10^6 counts per second. The counts are Rate-versus-Rate (R v R) corrected.

Figure S4. As described in Text S5, figure illustrating the use of the JEDI witness detectors (bottom panel) to determine when JEDI electron measurements are dominated by > 6-15 MeV electrons that penetrate the side walls of the JEDI instrument. Also, as discussed in Text S9, illustration of electron “accidentals” contamination of proton measurements (2nd panel) and heavy ion measurements (top panel).

Figure S5. Electron pitch angle distributions measured by JEDI in the polar caps of Jupiter’s polar regions where there are extremely narrow, upward going, magnetic field-aligned electron beams (Mauk et al., 2017a). This figure is intended to indicate that, because of internal scattering within the JEDI sensor volume, there are shoulders on the distributions that likely result from internal scattering rather than from electrons entering the sensor from those off-beam directions. These distributions are the energy-averaged differential number intensities, averaged over 30 – 1000 keV.

Figure S6. As described in Text S8, figure illustrating how energetic protons can very occasionally contaminate electron measurements.

Figure S7. As described in Text S9, figure illustrating the occurrence of false populations resulting from contamination by electron-induced accidentals in the ion measurements, as revealed in the bottom two panels. The ions labeled with "acc" are presumed to be false at all pitch angles and energies.

Figure S8. Selected proton upward propagating spectra that combine TOFxPH data (< 50 keV) and TOFxE data (> 50 keV) in a region over Jupiter’s main aurora. The top panel demonstrates how the efficiency of TOFxPH measurements drops precipitously as the energy decreases (compare the intensities with the counts). Both panels reveal the contamination at the lowest energies from “accidentals”. The “universal” accidentals spectrum (Equation 9) has been placed over the measured spectra there. From Mauk et al., (2023).

Figure S9. Representations of the variability of the responses of the Small Pixels of the electron solid state detectors relative to the responses of the electron Large Pixels. There are non-linear effects in the Small Pixel responses leading to substantial variability. The solid black line in the top panel, converted to an effective efficiency in the bottom panel, shows the choice that we have made for future conversion of the small pixel rates into intensities. The extension beyond 1 MeV is provided only to show that the polynomial fit does not misbehave terribly at higher energies. The less than 28 keV portion was tailored to better accommodate the polynomial fit.

Figure S10. One page from the online JEDI Survey Plots (<http://sd-www.jhuapl.edu/jedi/data/webapp/>.) showing examples of the data spikes introduced by the high cadence application of the JEDI Single Event Upset (SEU) detection mode.

Figure S11. Evaluations of total Microchannel Plate Detection efficiencies as described in Text S10 Item 25. Blue dots are for JEDI-270 and red dots are for JEDI-90. The procedure for making these evaluations must assume that the particle events are dominated by protons. The substantial scatter in these evaluations is most likely due to heavy ion contributions (leading to increases over proton expectations) and some electron contributions (leading to decreases under proton expectations). After 2017, our interpretation of these results is that the proton ~ 100 keV total efficiency is roughly 0.3, but there is uncertainty.

Table S1: Energy loss by protons in foils plus the 2 mm Al flashing on electron SSDs

Proton Energy (keV)	Electron Contam. Energy (keV)	Energy Lost (keV)
200	-112	311
223	-76	299
249	-37	286
278	6	272
310	52	259
347	102	244
387	157	230
433	216	216
483	281	202
540	351	189
603	427	176
673	510	163
752	600	151
839	699	140
938	808	129
1047	928	119
1169	1060	110
1306	1205	101
1459	1366	93
1629	1544	85
1820	1741	78
2032	1960	72
2270	2204	66
2535	2474	61
2831	2775	56
3162	3111	51
3532	3485	47
3945	3901	44
4406	4365	40
4920	4883	37
5495	5461	34
6138	6106	32

Table S2: Fits to time-of-flight versus input energy in keV

Time-of-Flight
 $\text{Log}_{10}(\text{TOF}(\text{ns})) = \text{P6}[\text{Log}_{10}(\text{Energy-into-sensor})]$

	H	He	O	S
a0	4.07022	6.67771	30.4431	22.8091
a1	-4.44458	-9.48197	-53.3389	-36.9054
a2	3.57637	8.05253	41.8469	27.7864
a3	-1.76968	-3.81436	-17.5368	-11.2656
a4	0.49005	0.996382	4.09294	2.55162
a5	-0.07096	-0.13564	-0.503966	-0.30573
a6	0.004173	0.007517	0.0255681	0.015132

Table S3: Calculations from Table S2 showing time-of-flight versus input energy in keV. Some nonsense values occur outside of the nominal range of JEDI.

EN(keV)	log10 EN	TOF in ns	TOF in ns	TOF in ns	TOF in ns
		H	He	O	S
4.65	0.67	181.81	963.40	1059770574.96	47654083.14
10.01	1.00	71.66	200.30	106192.38	48239.26
21.56	1.33	38.04	84.85	1272.75	1433.18
27.14	1.43	32.43	70.47	587.81	747.52
34.17	1.53	27.88	59.66	321.60	442.71
43.02	1.63	24.12	51.21	200.87	290.12
54.16	1.73	20.97	44.37	138.89	205.86
68.18	1.83	18.29	38.68	103.68	155.33
85.84	1.93	16.00	33.85	81.86	122.80
108.06	2.03	14.03	29.69	67.28	100.49
136.04	2.13	12.33	26.08	56.84	84.33
171.26	2.23	10.85	22.92	48.90	72.03
192.16	2.28	10.19	21.49	45.56	66.89
215.61	2.33	9.57	20.15	42.54	62.27
241.92	2.38	8.99	18.90	39.78	58.08
271.44	2.43	8.45	17.73	37.25	54.25
304.56	2.48	7.95	16.64	34.91	50.74
341.72	2.53	7.48	15.61	32.73	47.50
383.41	2.58	7.04	14.65	30.70	44.50
430.20	2.63	6.63	13.76	28.80	41.72
482.69	2.68	6.24	12.92	27.02	39.12
541.58	2.73	5.88	12.14	25.36	36.70
607.67	2.78	5.55	11.41	23.80	34.44
681.82	2.83	5.23	10.73	22.35	32.33
765.01	2.88	4.94	10.10	20.98	30.35
858.35	2.93	4.66	9.50	19.70	28.51
963.09	2.98	4.40	8.95	18.51	26.78
1080.60	3.03	4.15	8.43	17.39	25.16
1212.46	3.08	3.92	7.94	16.34	23.64
1360.40	3.13	3.71	7.49	15.37	22.22
1526.39	3.18	3.50	7.06	14.46	20.90
1712.64	3.23	3.31	6.66	13.61	19.65
1921.62	3.28	3.13	6.29	12.81	18.49
2156.09	3.33	2.96	5.94	12.07	17.40
2419.17	3.38	2.80	5.60	11.37	16.38
2714.35	3.43	2.64	5.29	10.72	15.43
3045.56	3.48	2.50	5.00	10.11	14.53

**Table S4: Fits to input energy versus SSD deposit energy by species (keV).
 $\text{Log}_{10}[\text{Input Energy}] = P6[\text{Log}_{10}(\text{SSD Deposited Energy})]$**

	e	H	He	O	S
a0	1.05307	1.25705	1.54463	1.2593	1.26368
a1	0.14046	0.171718	-0.34265	2.27329	2.42085
a2	-0.37383	0.087186	0.579905	-2.62401	-2.82329
a3	0.647852	-0.00453	-0.18774	1.49633	1.63798
a4	-0.27455	0.027604	0.043237	-0.40407	-0.45697
a5	0.049721	-0.00954	-0.00547	0.053539	0.063008
a6	-0.00335	0.000892	0.000268	-0.00281	-0.00345

Table S5: Calculations of input energy versus SSD deposit energy by species using Table S4. Electrons have 2 mm AL flashing on SSDs. Ion have bare SSDs.

		$\text{Log}_{10}[\text{Input Energy}] = P6[\text{Log}_{10}(\text{SSD Deposited Energy})]$				
Deposit		KeV	KeV	KeV	KeV	KeV
SSD En (keV)	$\text{log}_{10}[\text{Deposit}]$	Electrons	Protons	Helium	Oxygen	Sulfur
10.00	1.00	17.35	33.91	42.87	112.61	126.42
12.59	1.10	19.49	37.33	47.26	116.45	130.89
15.85	1.20	22.24	41.40	52.59	120.59	135.68
19.95	1.30	25.79	46.28	59.05	125.49	141.33
25.12	1.40	30.35	52.16	66.84	131.62	148.35
31.62	1.50	36.19	59.29	76.24	139.43	157.23
39.81	1.60	43.68	67.96	87.59	149.38	168.53
50.12	1.70	53.26	78.58	101.29	162.04	182.81
63.10	1.80	65.52	91.63	117.89	178.04	200.79
79.43	1.90	81.20	107.76	138.02	198.17	223.29
100.00	2.00	101.23	127.77	162.51	223.40	251.33
125.89	2.10	126.77	152.72	192.40	254.94	286.18
158.49	2.20	159.26	183.93	228.96	294.31	329.39
199.53	2.30	200.51	223.11	273.83	343.42	382.89
251.19	2.40	252.74	272.47	329.07	404.65	449.07
316.23	2.50	318.70	334.80	397.26	480.98	530.88
398.11	2.60	401.79	413.67	481.70	576.13	631.97
501.19	2.70	506.21	513.62	586.56	694.72	756.82
630.96	2.80	637.22	640.39	717.12	842.51	910.97
794.33	2.90	801.34	801.24	880.10	1026.64	1101.26
1000.00	3.00	1006.84	1005.28	1084.03	1255.96	1336.13
1258.93	3.10	1264.16	1263.87	1339.76	1541.43	1626.08
1584.89	3.20	1586.62	1591.19	1661.06	1896.69	1984.14
1995.26	3.30	1991.30	2004.81	2065.41	2338.70	2426.66
2511.89	3.40	2500.18	2526.44	2574.99	2888.59	2974.16

Table S6. JEDI Geometric Factors (cm² ster) for data generated after 21 Jan. 2026

NEW				sector 0	sector 1	sector 2	sector 3	sector 4	sector 5
JED90 §	SSD	large	electron	9.31E-04	9.82E-04	7.69E-04	1.00E-03	9.67E-04	8.02E-04
JED90	SSD	large	ion	5.68E-04	8.32E-04	9.81E-04	6.46E-04	1.00E-03	9.62E-04
JED90	SSD	small	electron	6.64E-05	6.77E-05	5.72E-05	6.90E-05	6.79E-05	6.05E-05
JED90	SSD	small	ion	3.91E-05	5.74E-05	6.76E-05	4.45E-05	6.90E-05	6.64E-05
JED90	TOFxE	large		6.90E-04	1.10E-03	1.02E-03	7.34E-04	7.52E-04	1.02E-03
JED90	TOFxE	small		4.76E-05	7.56E-05	7.01E-05	5.06E-05	5.18E-05	7.01E-05
JED90 *	TOF only			2.53E-03	3.32E-03	2.52E-03	2.60E-03	2.05E-03	2.59E-03
JED18	SSD	large	electron	6.50E-04	9.82E-04	7.69E-04	1.00E-03	9.67E-04	8.02E-04
JED18 &	SSD	large	ion	1.66E-04	7.49E-04	9.81E-04	5.81E-04	1.00E-03	9.62E-04
JED18	SSD	small	electron	4.64E-05	6.77E-05	5.72E-05	6.90E-05	6.79E-05	6.05E-05
JED18 #	SSD	small	ion	1.14E-05	5.74E-05	6.76E-05	4.45E-05	6.90E-05	6.64E-05
JED18	TOFxE	large		1.66E-04	8.84E-04	1.07E-03	6.49E-04	8.29E-04	1.02E-03
JED18 #	TOFxE	small		1.14E-05	6.77E-05	7.35E-05	4.97E-05	5.72E-05	7.01E-05
JED18 *	TOF only			1.13E-03	2.84E-03	2.64E-03	2.45E-03	2.27E-03	2.59E-03
JED27	SSD	large	electron	9.31E-04	9.82E-04	7.69E-04	1.00E-03	9.67E-04	8.02E-04
JED27	SSD	large	ion	5.68E-04	8.32E-04	9.81E-04	6.46E-04	1.00E-03	9.62E-04
JED27	SSD	small	electron	6.64E-05	6.77E-05	5.72E-05	6.90E-05	6.79E-05	6.05E-05
JED27	SSD	small	ion	3.91E-05	5.74E-05	6.76E-05	4.45E-05	6.90E-05	6.64E-05
JED27	TOFxE	large		6.37E-04	8.67E-04	1.11E-03	7.08E-04	9.07E-04	1.02E-03
JED27	TOFxE	small		4.39E-05	5.98E-05	7.69E-05	4.88E-05	6.25E-05	7.01E-05
JED27 *	TOF only			2.34E-03	2.62E-03	2.76E-03	2.50E-03	2.48E-03	2.59E-03

* The "TOF only" G depends on an onboard setable "decimation factor". For this chart, that factor was set to F = 1.

This factor reduces the effective geometric factor by that factor of F.

& Large Ion SSD #5 (RED) failed due to a HV anomaly long prior to entering Jupiter's magnetosphere

Red values are shielded witness detectors. Large Ion and TOFxE pixels reduced by additional 10% due to blockage.

§ Large JEDI-90 electron SSD Sector 0 (RED) failed at the beginning of May 2023 due to a HV anomaly